

A SHORT REVIEW ON VIBRATIONAL SPECTROSCOPY**Dr. Ranu Chaturvedi**Faculty, Department of P.G. Studies & Research in Chemistry
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Rani Durgavati University, Jabalpur**ABSTRACT**

Spectroscopy/spectrometry is often used in physical and analytical chemistry for the identification of substances through the spectrum emitted from or absorbed by them. Infrared spectroscopy is one of the most powerful analytical techniques which provides information on molecular vibrations or more princely on transition between vibrational and rotational energy levels in molecules. The term vibrational spectroscopy is used to describe the techniques of infrared and raman spectroscopy. Present study is helpful in clearly understanding the basic principles and applications of vibrational spectroscopy. In the present study, most of the application of infrared spectroscopy has been taken into account. However such studies are very extensive and can make the work easier in the upcoming projects.

Keywords: spectroscopy, IR, principle, application

INTRODUCTION

Spectroscopy is the study of the interaction between matter and electromagnetic radiation. it is the technique of splitting light into its constituent wavelengths (a spectrum), in

much the same way as a prism splits light into a rainbow of colours. However, in general, a spectrum is generally more than a simple 'rainbow' of colours.[fig 1].Old style spectroscopy was carried out using a prism and photographic plates. These days,

modern spectroscopy uses diffraction gratings to disperse the light, which is then projected onto CCDs (Charge Coupled Devices) similar to those used in digital cameras [1].

Fig 1

Spectroscopy/spectrometry is often used in physical and analytical chemistry for the identification of substances through the spectrum emitted from or absorbed by them. Spectroscopy/spectrometry is also heavily used in astronomy and remote sensing. Most large telescopes have spectrometers, which are used either to measure the chemical composition and physical properties of astronomical objects or to measure their velocities from the Doppler shift of their spectral lines[2].

ELECTROMAGNETIC RADIATION

Maxwell proposed that the light consisted of electromagnetic waves. Electromagnetic radiation is considered as being produced by the oscillating motion of an electric charge. This oscillation results in a periodically changing electric field surrounding the charge, and also produces an oscillating magnetic field [3]. These *oscillating electric and magnetic and magnetic field disturbance both are perpendicular to each other and propagate through space as radiation*. The electromagnetic radiation consists of various forms of radiation such as UV, Infrared, X-ray, radio frequency etc. The frequency and wavelength of electromagnetic radiation varies over many orders of magnitude [4]. The electromagnetic spectrum is the range of all possible frequencies of electromagnetic radiation, each of which can be considered as a wave or particle travelling at the speed of light, often referred to as a photon. These waves differ from each other in length and frequency. The electromagnetic spectrum is divided according to the type of atomic or molecular transition that gives rise to the absorption or emission of photons in UV, IR, microwave, radio wave etc regions of electromagnetic radiations as shown in fig 3[5].

Electromagnetic Radiation

Fig 2

CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF ELECTROMAGNETIC RADIATION

Every form of electromagnetic radiation including visible light oscillates in a periodic fashion with peak and valley and displaying a characteristic amplitude

Frequency vs. Wavelength

(NOTE: Frequency refers to the number of crests of waves of same wavelength that pass by a point in one second.)

wavelength, and frequency that defines the direction.

Fig.4: Relationship between frequency and wavelength.

The number of wave cycles that pass through a point in one second (Measured in Hertz (Hz)) is defined as

frequency and wavelength (λ) is the length of one complete wave cycle (cm). Frequency and wavelength are inverse related (Equation 1):

$$v = c/\lambda \quad \text{-- (1)}$$

Where: c = speed of light 3×10^{10} cm/sec

The energy of a photon (E in Joules) related to wavelength and frequency follows (Equation 2): $E = hv = hc/\lambda$ -- (2)

Where: h = Planck's constant 6.6×10^{-34} Joules-sec

Above equations reveals that energy is directly proportional to frequency therefore, high energy radiation will have high frequency [6] and energy is inversely proportional to wavelength, hence, short wavelengths are high energy and vice versa.

TYPES OF SPECTRUM

1. **Absorption spectrum:** When the light emitted from a source is made to pass through an absorbing material and then examined with a spectrometer, the obtained spectrum is called absorption spectrum. It is the characteristics of the absorbing material. [fig.6]
2. **Emission spectrum:** when the light emitted directly from a source is examined

with a spectrometer, the emission spectrum is obtained. Every source has its own characteristics emission spectrum [6].

analyte; a process that requires a much greater energy input [7].

Infrared spectroscopy is one of the most

**ABSORPTION
SPECTROSCOPY**

**EMISSION
SPECTROSCOPY**

Absorption spectroscopy relies on the absorption of energy from a photon which subsequently promotes a lower-energy state to a higher-energy, or excited, state. As the energy of the photon changes the type of transition that the analyte undergoes will change. For example in IR spectroscopy, the absorption of relatively low IR radiation results in the vibration of chemical bonds within the analyte; a process which requires a fairly low energy input.[fig 7]Whereas, higher energy photons, such as those found in the UV-visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum, will promote valence electrons to move from their ground state to excited state energy levels within the atoms of an

powerful analytical techniques which provides information on molecular vibrations or more princely on transition between vibrational and rotational energy levels in molecules. The term vibrational spectroscopy is used to describe the techniques of infrared and roman spectroscopy. In fact, atoms in a molecule actually do not remain in a fixed relative positions but vibrate about their mean position. Thus, absorption of radiation will increase the vibrational energy of the molecules and give rise to vibrational spectra. The absorption of infrared ration is a quantized process. A molecule absorbs only selected frequencies (energies) of infrared radiation. The absorption of infrared radiation corresponds to energy

changes of the order of 8 to 40 kJ/mole. Radiation in this energy range corresponds to the encompassing and stretching and bending vibrational frequencies of the bonds in most covalent molecules. In absorption process, those frequencies of infrared radiation that match the natural vibrational frequencies of the molecule are absorbed, and the energy absorbed serves to increase the **amplitude** of the vibrational motions of the bond in the molecule. However, not all bonds in a molecule are capable of absorbing infrared energy, even if the frequency of the radiation exactly matches that of the bond motion. Only those bonds that have a **dipole moment** that changes as a function of time are capable of absorbing infrared radiation. Absorption of radiation not only increase the vibrational energy but also rotational energy is changed[8].

INFRARED REGIONS: Infrared spectroscopy is one of the most useful and widely used methods to perform structural analysis. Given that the molecule under investigation is infrared active, (i.e. it absorbs Infrared radiation), then different

types of structural information can be obtained.[fig 8(a & b)]. The infrared radiation refers broadly to that part of electromagnetic spectrum which lies between visible and microwave regions. The IR region has been subdivided as follows:

1. **The photographic region.** This ranges from visible to 0.8μ (1 micron, $\mu=10^{-3}$ mm or 10^{-4} cm)
2. **The near infrared region (overtone region).** It ranges from 0.8 to 2.5μ ($12500-4000\text{cm}^{-1}$) and gas energies in the range 154.8 to $41.84 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (37 to $10 \text{ k Cal mol}^{-1}$). Near infrared region exhibits bands assignable to **harmonic** overtones of fundamental and combination bands.
3. **The mid infrared region (vibration-rotation region).** It ranges from 2.5 to 15μ ($4000-667 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and corresponds to energies in the range 41.84 to $4.184 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (10 to $1.0 \text{ k Cal mol}^{-1}$). This region is particularly important for structural work since the vibration induced in organic molecule are absorbed in this region. Vibrational and rotational transition occur in this region.

4. **The far infrared region (Rotation region).** This range from 15 to 200 μ (667 to 50 cm^{-1}) and corresponds to energies in the range 4.184 to 0.4184 kJ mol^{-1} (1.0 to 0.1 k Cal mol^{-1}).

less separation. Changes in electronic energy involve larger quanta, changes in vibrational energy involve smaller quanta and changes in rotational energy require smallest quanta.

Vibrations of molecules containing heavy atoms, molecular skeleton vibrations and crystal lattice vibrations[6].

PRINCIPLE OF IR SPECTROSCOPY

A molecule contains electronic, vibrational and rotational; energy levels. Each electronic level, within a molecule, is associated with a number of vibrational levels with less energy separations and each vibrational level in turn is associated with a set of rotational levels with even

Due to relatively smaller amount energy associate with the infrared radiation, they are incapable of electronic excitations but induce transition between vibrational and rotational energy levels of a molecule. Hence infrared spectrum results from transitions between vibrational and rotational energy levels and is called **vibrational- rotational spectrum** of the molecule [9].

The absorption of infrared causes the excitation of molecule from lower to the higher vibrational level. All the bonds

in a molecule are not capable of absorbing infrared light but only those bonds which are accompanied by a *change in dipole moment* will absorb in the infrared region. Infrared light is thus absorbed when the oscillating dipole moment interacts with the oscillating electric vector of the infrared beam. These vibrations absorb infrared radiation at certain quantized frequencies and give rise to characteristic bands. When infrared light of that frequency is incident to the molecule energy is absorbed and the amplitude of that vibration is increased. Vibrational transitions which are accompanied by a change in dipole moment of the molecule are called **infrared active** transitions. On the other hand vibrational transitions which do not involve change in dipole moment of the molecule are not directly observed and these are called **infrared inactive**. An infrared spectrum is obtained when the frequency of molecular vibration corresponds to frequency of infrared radiation absorbed.

Infrared spectrum of a compound represents its energy absorption pattern in the infrared region expressed in terms of wavelength (λ) or wavenumber ($\bar{\nu}$). Mostly **infrared spectra** are plotted as percent absorbance or transmittance against wave

number. Frequencies are usually expressed in terms of wave number (in cm^{-1}) since the number is directly proportional to frequency and therefore to the energy ($E = h\nu = hc/\lambda = hc\bar{\nu}$) while wavelength is inversely proportional to the energy [9].

MODES OF VIBRATIONS

When a molecule absorbs infrared radiations, it is set into vibrations resulting in excitation of bond deformations either stretching or bending.

1. **Stretching vibrations:** A stretching vibration is a rhythmical movement where the distance between two atoms increases or decreases but the atoms remain in the same bond axis. As this type of vibrations corresponds to one-dimensional motion so there will be $(n-1)$ stretching vibrations for non-cyclic systems. Stretching vibrations require higher energies and occur at higher frequencies. These are two types:
 - a) **Symmetric stretching:** In symmetric stretching, both the atoms move in and out simultaneously, that is, stretching and compression occur in a symmetrical fashion.
 - b) **Asymmetric stretching:** In this mode, one atom approaches the central atom while the other departs from it, that is, one bond

is compressing while the other is stretching.

2. **Bending vibrations (deformation):** The distance between the atoms remains constant but the position of the atoms changes relative to the original bond axis. Thus bending involves oscillation of the atoms perpendicular to its chemical bond. As these vibrations describe two-dimensional motions, there will be $(2n-5)$ bending vibrations for non-cyclic and linear molecules. Bending vibrations requires lower energy and occur at lower frequency. These are four types:

- Scissoring:** Here the two atoms joined to the central atom move toward and away from each other with the deformation of the valence angle (**in plane bending**).
- Rocking:** Here the structural unit swings back and forth in the plane of the molecule (**in plane bending**).
- Wagging:** The structural unit swings back and forth out of the plane of the molecule (**out of plane bending**).

d) **Twisting:** Here the structural units rotate about the bond which joins to the rest of the molecule (**out of plane bending**).[9]

A molecule that is infrared active must undergo a change in its dipole moment when vibrating. The simplest modes of vibration that are infrared active are stretching and bending modes[10].

MOLECULAR VIBRATION

The absorption of light will increase both amplitude and frequency of molecular vibrations. When the radiant energy matches the energy of a specific molecular vibration, absorption occurs. Molecules with a permanent dipole moment, such as water, HCl, and NO, are infrared active.

Ex. HCl – IR active

The O₂ molecule does not possess a permanent dipole moment, so it is not infrared active.

In the case of alkenes (C=C) and alkynes (C≡C) if the bond is symmetrically substituted no band will be seen in the IR spectrum, however, if the bond is asymmetrically substituted a stretching

frequency corresponding to the alkene or alkyne bond will be present (Table 2).

Oscillator	Wavenumber (cm^{-1})
C-H	3320-2700
-C=C-	1690-1590
C=O	1870-1590
C-O	1300-1050
C $\equiv$ C	2250-2150
C-Cl	800-600

Table[2]: Wavenumbers for selected diatomic oscillators.

In order to understand molecular vibrations, a bond can be treated as a simple harmonic oscillator composed of two masses (atoms) joined by a spring. Figure [10] depicts a diatomic molecule with two generic atoms (of masses m_1 and m_2) connected by a spring[6].

Figure10; Representation of a polyatomic molecule

Figure11: Representation of a diatomic molecule. If masses m_1 and m_2 are equal, no change in the dipole moment will occur as the molecule vibrates.

Selection Rule for Infrared Transitions:

For a particular vibration to be infrared active there must be a change in the dipole-moment of the molecule during the vibration. In other words transition dipole moment must not be zero. Homonuclear diatomic molecules are inactive in the infrared spectrum. They do not have a dipole moment to start with and during the vibration also the dipole moment is zero.

E.g.: H_2 , O_2 , N_2 etc.

Heteronuclear diatomic molecule such as CO , NO are active in IR. Symmetrical polyatomic molecules such as CO_2 , the symmetric stretching vibration is infrared inactive whereas the asymmetric stretching vibration is IR active. In addition to the above, for IR spectroscopy $\Delta v = \pm 1$ i.e., transition can take place between adjacent vibrational levels, 0 to 1, 1 to 2 etc.[6]

ENERGY EQUATION OF IR SPECTRUM

The energy of simple harmonic oscillator is quantized and is given by (Equation 1):

$$E_n = (n+1/2)h\nu \text{-----(1)}$$

Where n is quantum number and has integral value as 0,1,2,3,.....

The classical vibrational frequency for a diatomic molecule (with force constant k and masses m_1 and m_2) has been derived from Hooke's Law (Equation 2):

$$\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} c \sqrt{k \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_1 + m_2}} \text{-----(2)}$$

Where:

$$\mu = \text{reduced mass} = \frac{m_1 + m_2}{m_1 m_2}$$

$$\nu = \text{Frequency in sec}^{-1}$$

In terms of the wavenumber ($\bar{\nu}$) (Equation 3):

$$\bar{\nu} = \frac{\nu}{c} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}} = \frac{1}{2\pi c} \sqrt{\frac{k(m_1 m_2)}{m_1 + m_2}} \text{-----}$$

-----(3)

Where:

$$c = \text{speed of light} = 3 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm/sec}$$

Instrumentation Of IR-The main parts of IR spectrometer are as follows:

1. Radiation Source

2. Sample Cells And Sampling Of Substances
3. Monochromators
4. Detectors
5. Recorder

1. **IR radiation sources** -IR instruments require a source of radiant energy which emit IR radiation which must be steady, intense enough for detection and extend over the desired wavelength.[fig 12] Various sources of IR radiations are as follows.

- a) Nernst glower
- b) Incandescent lamp
- c) Mercury arc
- d) Tungsten lamp
- e) Global source
- f) Nichrome wire

2. Sample Cells And Sampling Of Substances

IR spectroscopy has been used for the characterization of solid, liquid or gas samples Various techniques are used for preparing solid samples such as pressed pellet technique, solid run in solution, solid films, mull technique etc. Liquidsamples can be held using a liquid sample cell made of alkali halides. Aqueous solvents cannot be used as they will dissolve alkali halides. Only organic solvents like chloroform can be used. Sampling of gas is similar to the sampling of liquids.

3. **Monochromators** – Various types of monochromators are prism, gratings and filters. Prisms are made of Potassium bromide, Sodium chloride or Caesium iodide. Filters are made up of Lithium Fluoride and Diffraction gratings are made up of alkali halides.
4. **Detectors** – Detectors are used to measure the intensity of unabsorbed infrared radiation. Detectors like thermocouples, Bolometers, thermistors, Golay cell, and pyro-electric detectors are used.
5. **Recorders** – Recorders are used to

record the IR spectrum[6]

The IR Spectrum

Historically, infrared spectra have been represented as percent of transmittance versus either the wavenumber or the wavelength. The use of wavenumbers, is standard, with the use of

wavelength (expressed in nm or μm) having fallen out of favor.

In terms of wavenumbers the infrared region spans from 33 to 12820 cm^{-1} . However, most infrared analyses are carried out in the mid-infrared region (4000 to 400 cm^{-1}).

By convention, the wavenumbers are plotted in decreasing order from left to right. A typical IR spectrum is illustrated in fig.

Dispersive IR Instruments

Most IR spectrometers can be

categorized into two classes: dispersive and Fourier Transform instruments. The basic design of a dispersive single beam instrument includes a source of infrared radiation, a monochromator, and the detector (Figure 14).

After interacting with the sample (or the blank), infrared radiation is

dispersed by a monochromator into its

individual frequency components and information on which frequencies were absorbed can be obtained using a photodiode array detector.

Sources and detectors for infrared radiation have limited stability; with light intensity and detector sensitivity changing over time, or with fluctuations in temperature etc. The blank (reference or background) and sample measurements should be made one after the other to ensure they are made under the same analytical conditions. This limitation is minimized by the use of double beam instruments which are capable of measuring the sample and reference simultaneously.

Double beam instruments use 'choppers' to control the path of the radiation, alternating between the sample and the reference (Figure 15). These instruments use the known speed of

rotation of the beam chopper to compare and resolve the information reaching the detector.

The use of an opaque surface provides the means for adjusting the 0% transmittance response of the detector.

Finally, it is easier to correct for absorption of infrared radiation by carbon dioxide and water (present within the instrument background) with double beam instruments than with their single beam counterparts.[5]

FOURIER TRANSFORMS INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FT-IR)

Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) is one of the techniques that are used today for measuring the intensity of infrared radiations as a function of frequency or wavelength. Infrared radiation is invisible electromagnetic radiation just below the red colour of the visible electromagnetic spectrum, with wavelength range from 700 nm to 1 nm. Until 1800s it was not recognized as a distinct part of the electromagnetic spectrum. The discovery of IR radiation was made by Sir William Hershel in 1800 when he measured the heating effect of the sunlight by using mercury thermometers with blackened bulbs. Hershel wanted to

know how much heat passed through the different coloured filtered that he used to observe sunlight. He found out that the temperature increased from violet through red and that is why he decided to measure the temperature in the region just beyond the red filter, where no sunlight was visible. Later at his surprise he found out that this region had the highest temperature of all colours. This fact leads to the conclusions that the molecules inside this thermometers absorb IR light more than any other colours of the spectrum that he measured. The reason for this behaviour of the molecules inside the thermometer which was not known to Hershel at that time.

Most of the components in present infrared spectrometers were already described during the nineteenth century. The field of infrared spectroscopy did not develop at that time due to the difficulties in building suitable detectors for measuring IR radiation.

In the beginning of the 20th century William W. Coblentz conducted measurements in the IR spectral region of the transitions between different vibrational states of molecules for hundreds of inorganics and organic

compounds. The recognitions of the hi potential of IR spectroscopy and advances in electronics during and af World War II led to establishing spectroscopy as a key analytical method academic and industrial labs by the mide of the 20th century. Most instrumentation used through the 197 was based on prism or grati monochromators.

A major breakthrough in spectroscopy was the introduction of F IR spectrometers which used instrument called interferometers that w discovered almost a century ago by Alb Michelson. At the time of the constructi of the Michelson interferometers (189 Lord Rayleigh recognized that the outp from an interferometers could converted to a spectrum using mathematical operation that was develop by the French mathematician Fourier the 1820s. The combination of the discoveries let to the development of whole new technology for measuring a calculating the IR spectrum which w used in FT-IR spectrometers. In spite the advantages of FT-IR over dispersi instrument such as: high speed da collection, increased resolution, low detection limits and greater ener

throughout the acceptance of FT-IR spectroscopy was slowed by the complexity of the calculation required to transform the measured data into a spectrum. With the discovery of the Fast Fourier Transform algorithm by James Cooley and John Tukey (1964) the time for spectrum calculation was reduced from hours to just a few seconds. The development of the first commercial FT-IR spectrometer in 1969 by Digi lab enabled spectroscopists to see a spectrum plotted shortly after the interferogram was collected. Today there are large number of commercial FT-IR spectrometers such as: quantitative analysis of complex mixtures in liquid, solid or gaseous state; determination of the quality of a sample; biological and biomedical spectroscopy.[8]

Fig.16: Operational Schematic of a Thermo Nicolet FTIR Instrument. Image reproduced with permission from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Madison, WI, USA).

Dispersive IR instruments operate in the frequency domain. There are, however, advantages to be gained from measurement in the time domain followed by computer transformation into the frequency domain whereas in Fourier-transform spectrometers, Any waveform

can be shown in one of two ways; either in *frequency domain* or *time domain*.

FTIR instruments have several advantages over dispersive IR instruments including:

Speed: All IR frequencies are measured simultaneously, resulting in measurements being taken in seconds rather than minutes. This is often referred to as the *Fulgent Advantage*.

Sensitivity: The detectors utilized in FTIR instruments are highly sensitive which results in lower signal to noise ratios. This is known as the *Jacqui not Advantage*.

Simplicity: The only moving part in an FTIR instrument is the mirror in the interferometer; therefore, there is very little need for mechanical maintenance.

Internal calibration: The internal laser is used to self-calibrate the moving mirror in the FTIR instrument negating any need for timely or complicated external calibration.

This is denoted as the *Connes Advantage*. [6]

With the knowledge of the fundamental Principles, it becomes easier to be appropriate in analysing different samples.

Infrared spectroscopy is the measurement of the wavelength and intensity of the absorption of mid-infrared light by a sample. Mid-infrared is energetic enough to excite molecular vibrations to higher energy levels. The wavelength of infrared absorption bands is characteristic of specific types of chemical bonds, and infrared spectroscopy finds its greatest utility for identification of organic and organometallic molecules. The high selectivity of the method makes the estimation of the sample in a complex matrix possible. Infrared spectroscopy is the measurement of the wavelength and intensity of the absorption of mid-infrared light by a sample. Mid-infrared is energetic enough to excite molecular vibrations to higher energy levels.

In order to predict equilibrium stable-isotope fractionations, it is necessary to know the characteristic frequencies of molecular vibrations. It is also necessary to know how much

each vibrational frequency in a molecule changes when a heavy isotope is substituted for a light one. Vibrational frequencies for isotopically substituted molecules are not always known, so it is often necessary to use some type of force-field model to predict them. Molecular vibrations are also important in understanding infrared absorption and the mechanisms and kinetics of chemical reactions. Frequencies are most commonly measured with infrared or Raman spectroscopy. Rotational-vibrational spectroscopy, isotope substitution, and many forms of force-field modeling are used to determine characteristic atomic motions.

Infrared spectroscopy is helpful in determining the relative stability of various conformations of cyclic compounds. Cyclohexane exist in both chair and boat forms and as per selection rules, there are 18 infrared active C-C stretch and CH₂ rocking and twisting vibrations possible for boat forms, but there are only five of these for the chair form. The spectral examination of cyclohexane in the region 1350-700 cm⁻¹ reveals five bands expected for chair form. This shows the greater stability of chair conformation over boat conformation[11]. IR spectroscopy is also

used to determine the geometrical Isomerism and rotational isomerism. For example the existence of gauche (skew) and staggered (trans) conformations of 1,2-dichloro ethane can be easily detected in its infrared spectrum. Two bands appear at 1291 cm⁻¹ and 1235 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of 1,2-dichloroethane

(CH ₂ rocking)	1291 cm ⁻¹
¹ (CH ₂ rocking)	

The staggered (trans) form predominates at lower temperature whereas gauche form dominates at higher temperature. The relative intensities of the bands depend upon temperature. The rocking vibration band of trans form at 1291 cm⁻¹ becomes less intense as the temperature is raised whereas the band at 1235 cm⁻¹ attributed to the gauche form becomes more intense. From the relative intensities of the bands, their relative abundance at a particular temperature can be estimated[12].

Infrared spectroscopy is also useful in the detection of impurity in a compound by comparing its spectrum with the spectrum of the authentic sample of the compound. Moreover, a pure sample always consists of sharp peaks and bands while impure will consist of poor bands and also some additional bands. For

example Benzene appears as a common impurity in cyclohexane[fig 10]. Its presence can be easily detected by its absorption at 255nm[13].

IR spectroscopy is also helpful in the analysis of inorganic compounds. Linkage and Geometrical Isomerism can easily be identified in complexes with the help of IR. In order to determine the shape or symmetry of the molecule and the presence or absence of water molecule. IR spectra of NO_2 gives three peaks at 750, 1323, 1616 cm^{-1} which are in accordance with the formula (3N-6). It clearly proves that NO_2 is bent molecule and not a linear molecule where vibrations should be observed according to (3N-5). These arguments have been extended to determine the shape of larger molecules. For example: IR spectra have elucidated the linear, square planar and octahedral structure of XeF_2 , XeF_4 and XeF_6 respectively. If a sample contains lattice water, its IR spectrum will contain three bands in the regions 3600-3200, 1650, 600-300 cm^{-1} . On the other hand, if water is coordinated to a metal ion, an additional band in the 880-650 cm^{-1} region is observed. Although IR spectrum clearly showed the presence of water in clathrate compound, $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\text{NH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ but it

could not be detected in a single crystal by X-ray study[14].

In addition to the above, a number of pharmaceutical substance can be identified, analysed and examined with the help of infrared spectroscopy. quantitative analysis involving the determination of Aspirin, Phenacetin and Caffeine (APC) in Analgesic Tablets is very important. In this analysis the drug content of appropriate number of ACP tablets are directly extracted into chloroform. The final concentration of chloroform solution is made in such a way that it should contain 90 mg/cm^3 of phenacetin and 13 mg/cm^3 of caffeine. The infrared spectra of aspirin, phenacetin and caffeine showed carbonyl bands at 1764, 1511, 1665 cm^{-1} respectively. FTIR spectrum of phenacetin, the first synthetic fever reducer, exhibited following bands.

Fig.2: IR of phenacetin

Similarly determination of Meprobamate, Codeine Phosphate in tablet have also been carried out. IR spectroscopy is also used in determination of Molecular Weight and crystallinity in industries[15].

Present study is helpful in clearly understanding the basic principles and applications of vibrational spectroscopy. In the present study, most of the application of infrared spectroscopy has been taken into account. However such studies are very extensive and can make the work easier in the upcoming projects.

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